

Editor in Chief

**Dr Adebayo Ola
AFOLARANMI**

Department of Religious
and Intercultural Studies,
Lead City University,
Ibadan, Nigeria

Editors

Assoc. Prof Adekunle

Olusola OTUNLA

Department of Mass
Communication and Media
Technology,
Lead City University,
Ibadan, Nigeria

Dr Michael

GBADEGESIN

Department of Languages
and Literature
Lead City University,
Ibadan, Nigeria

Associate Editors

Dr Emmanuel O.

MALOMO

ECWA Gospel Centre,
Kano, Nigeria

Rebecca Oluwatosin

BANJO

Department of Peace
Studies and Conflicts
Resolution, Ajayi Crowther
University, Oyo, Nigeria

Emmanuel Selome

FASINU

Department of Political
Science, Wesley University,
Ondo, Nigeria

© 2025 Authors

**Religious Exemplifications as Post-
Colonial Dialogue in Ahmed Yerima's
*The Angel and The Bishop***

Olumuyiwa Paul OLAYINKA, PhD

*Languages and Literature Department, Lead City
University, Ibadan.*

paulolumuyiwa1981@gmail.com, +2348050991066

Rebecca Ufuoma DAVIES, PhD

*Languages and Literature Department, Lead City
University, Ibadan.*

ufuomarebecca@gmail.com, +2348066541622

Olukemi Bolade ADESINA, PhD

*Languages and Literature Department, Lead City
University, Ibadan.*

kemisolade@gmail.com, +2348036683600

Abstract

The thematic preoccupation of dramatic endeavours among most African playwrights often highlight lived experiences of Africans. Therefore, the theatre space provides the avenue where such lived experiences are re-enacted, and challenged. Ahmed Yerima's theatrical endeavour follows in this pursuit, with creative dimensions. The objective of the study is to examine the selected plays of Ahmed Yerima as his perspective to the reality of religious malpractices, a major part of the bane of post-independence Nigeria that has hampered growth and development. The theoretical framework for the work is New Historicism, which argues essentially that every literary text is a product, reflection and refraction of actual historical realities. New Historicism is utilised to situate the plays in context, with thematic discourse, characterisation and dramatic techniques deployed for elucidation. The study accentuates plays-texts,

as veritable tools for national sustainable development. The study discovers that religion among other things is lading with corruption, immorality hypocrisy and essentially, that religion is only used by most people as a coping strategy for post/neocolonial problems.

Keywords: Dramatic Endeavours, Religious Malpractices, Post-Independence Realities, New Historicism, Sustainable Development

Introduction

The harsh lived experiences of Nigerians in post-independence Nigeria is a common springboard of Nigerian literature. According to Agboola (2020), Nigerian playwrights have continued to reflect and refract on the social, political and economic rupture that has characterised the nation since independence in 1960 concluded Olayinka 2023 & 2024). The purpose of this work is to investigate the postcolonial theme of religious malpractices that are brought to the fore in selected Ahmed Yerima's plays.

Olayinka (2024) submits that the zeal and hope of self-determinism with which the nationalists fought the imperialists began to wane because the atrocities of the indigenous 'militicians' who seized the reins of power in Nigeria almost triple that of the colonialists. Thus, the desire for the tiger to display its tigritude died an abrupt death. The overbearing drive to display the rich cultural heritage of the empire also collapsed. In fact, the empire has no one to write back to outside the country as the oppressors are among the kith and kin. While the first generation of Nigerian playwrights engaged the imperialists, the second-generation deployed Marxism to fight the internal oppressors, the third generation of playwright, that Yerima belongs, have continued to focus on the individual with the intention of dramatizing the effects of the post and neo-colonial disenchantment on them.

The Angel and *The Bishop* are used to discuss Ahmed Yerima's treatment of postcolonial reality of religious malpractices. Both titles are qualified for such because of their fidelity to the actuality of the theme.

Theoretical Framework

New Historicism, which has been described as almost the greatest ground-breaking critical movement, came into existence in 1980 (Adeyemi, 2021). It came into being because of the critical philosophy of Stephen Greenblatt a literary critic, theorist and scholar of global standing, who created this exact

term New Historicism for the first time with an aim to promulgate new critical approaches for reading the texts of the Renaissance era. Despite the fact that German authors like Herder helped launch historicism at the end of the eighteenth century, the movement persisted in the nineteenth century as a result of the concerted efforts of historians such as Dilthey, R. G Collingwood, Hans Georg Gadamer, Ernst Cassirer, and Karl Mannheim (Noon, 2021). While literary historians like Sainte-Beuve and Hippolyte Taine made the decision to view literary texts as unquestionably influenced by their historical context, Hegel and Marx, who themselves had an unparalleled impact on historicist thinking, articulated very deliberate historical modes of historical analysis. There is a plethora of things that we classify as "New." Historicism is not fundamentally new; rather, it is a return to particular analytical focuses that have been fostered by earlier historical traditions (Adeyemi, 2021).

New historicism as a critical approach is a disruption of the extreme formal and verbal critical canon and intransigence of close textual analysis of a work at the expense of extrinsic value embedded implicitly in its intrinsic part (Chalse, 2022). Unlike, Formalists and Structuralists, New Historicists believe that to pinpoint only linguistic and stylistic features of a piece of writing is to see one side of the coin, whereas a text finds suitable explanation only when the circumstances of its construction are also reviewed. New Historicism is an approach to literary criticism and literary theory which is built on the principle that a literary work should be considered a creation of its time, place and circumstances of its composition rather than as an isolated production of an individual talent (Salman, 2021). In other words, New Historicism is an approach to literary analysis that considers the historical context of a piece. Since New Historicism just reflects a return to certain analytical attempts made possible by earlier traditions of historicism, the concept is not new. All systems of thinking, all phenomena, all institutions, all works of art, and all literary texts must be located within a historical context. This is the most strategic of New Historicism's objectives and traits. In other words, historical writings or phenomena cannot be isolated from history and studied independently of history. According to New Historicists, the form and substance of texts are dictated by their unique historical conditions as well as by their unique placement in time and space. As a result, we cannot apply the same presumptions and methodologies to Soyinka's analysis that we do to

Shakespeare's because their social, political, and economic contexts will have a significant impact on how they view truth, art, and politics and how their works will ultimately be interpreted by readers. To put it another way, literature must be understood in the framework of culture as a whole as well as in the settings of other discourses spanning politics, religion, and aesthetics (Salman, 2022).

A second characteristic of historicism is the belief that history sometimes operates in accordance with observable rules, providing predictability and explanatory capacity. Hegel's and Marx's ideas are particularly prominent in this regard. The idea that civilizations and cultures separated in time have different values and beliefs gives rise to a third issue: how can the historian 'know' the past? How can the historian go over her own worldview's limitations and wide range of presumptions and ideas to develop an empathic knowledge of a different culture? How can we resist imposing our own cultural biases, as well as our own goals and objectives, on writings that have been historically alien to us?

The current researcher agrees with New Historicists just as Wole Soyinka does. This is so because, New Historicism accounts for the contexts in the production, criticism and consumption of literary works. History would have been useless if we do not have lessons we can draw from it both for now and the future (Olayinka, 2023; Salman 2021).

An important thing to foreground here is that history textbooks are essentially different from historical plays. Also, to create a line of difference between history materials and historical drama, some theoretical establishments have been formulated. These have pointed out that historical dramas though have drawn copiously from history are purely creatively produced by the playwright who has employed various methods to fabricate a distinctive text from history which serves as the main raw material. With the help of theory, we have been given tools to delineate between historical plays and history. We can identify both the points of contacts and the points of departure between the two (Olayinka 2023).

Incidentally, Yerima described the playwrights, in one of his plethora of published critical essays, as both a bard, a prophet, and a monarch. He asserts that a creative writer can be seen as a bard because of his duties as the custodian, not owner, of the oral traditions and the one who can perform it with or without notice. He serves as prophet-seer to his people because he can foresee and predict impending events, either good or evil,

looming on the society wherein he operates. Furthermore, he is of the opinion that the society is the producers of these monarchs because they came to being by them and since they come by the instrumentation of the society, they not only can feel and see the burden of the society in a personal way, they also carry it in such ways that it becomes personal and private to them. The creative gifts they possess make them rulers of sort and they rule and reign among their peers by the word power they wield. Many a time, they fell flat in the pursuit of their fate given duty, and a in a number of times they soar. In either case, these society made monarchs continued to keep working at their destiny with a certain hope that a time will definitely appear that their vision of a prosperous and peaceful society will become a reality. Among the creative king-ruler in Nigeria are Wole Soyinka, Femi Osofisan, Ahmed Yerima. They are so described because they continue to invest their creative prowess and word powers into the service of the society (Olayinka, 2023).

Whereas, drama has been conceived as the genre of literature which re-enacts an imaginary action and or event, on stage, it can however also be a record of real lived experience of a people which is being reproduced on stage for current or a future audience. The thoughts and position of the current investigator is that although a drama text can consist of imaginary materials, a pocket of real events and personalities will always be found here and there in the overall play. The playwright often uses fictional elements like songs, dance, costumes, characters which often replicate real historical situations to create a sense of reality which the audience can relate to in his play. Sequel to this, every playwright who desires to utilise contextual materials must seek not only to observe but also to uphold the fundamentals of history which will enhance an objective though critical and fresh dramatic produce eventually. One of these is the fact that certain facts and figures of history which his people hold sacrosanct must not be distorted in order not to incur the wrath of the same people he tries to reach. Although, the playwright seems to enjoy certain unwritten code that ensures they have freedom just like their colleagues in other genres of literature to tamper with history to enhance their creativity and service to the society. The capacity of each drama practitioners to creatively and objectively bend history that separates one dramatist from another even when both have employed the same historical material in their works. We

can immediately cite examples of some certain history dependent plays in Nigeria (Olayinka, 2023).

Our aim, drawing from the views of New Historicists and Wole Soyinka, is to investigate a carefully selected dramatic works of Ahmed Yerima based on re-enactment of specific lived experiences, which translate to historical realities discernible in the plays we have selected for scrutiny. The explicit occurrence of historical realities in the selected drama texts has supported and stimulated our choice them of them, Therefore, African playwrights in an attempt to proffer solution to the problems common people live with seem to be perpetually handcuffed to daily historical realities of their people. This has made the study of African drama fairly predictable. It is often always about how an author has employed history for the betterment of the contemporary time (Olayinka, 2023). This is the reason that African drama is easily studied using theories like New Historicism that give allowance for the social, economic and political context from which literary works emerge (Adeyemi, 2021).

The reason for the success attained by Yerima at the employment of socio, political and economic contexts just like his predecessors and contemporaries can be traced to many factors which include the fact that the contexts they have been enacting in their works are really neither past, passed away, far away, long gone, forgotten nor desirable than the present. The so-called historical contexts stubbornly have continued to live and even reinvent itself. For example, the perennial religious corruption, reported or not, in Nigeria points largely to the fact that history to Africans is not a past thing. History is very much alive and fresh. The selected religious inclined plays for this study all have one theme in common among other themes; the hypocrisy of religious practitioners, either as leaders or followers. Most of the studies on post-colonial realities have focused more on governmental corrupt practices while only a scanty work exists on the reality of corruption in religious circles, hence this study.

Aim of the Study

The aim of the study is to identify and discuss the instances of corruption in selected religious plays of Ahmed Yerima.

Literature Review

Corrupt Practices in the religious cycles is a major postcolonial theme that Yerima dramatises in some of his works as observed by Olayinka (2023). In a work published in Mbaegbu (2024) submits that “Faith and religion are central to Nigerian life”. This, in essence, means that religion and the nation of Nigeria are inseparable. Almost every aspect of our national life is permeated with religion. For instance, at every state function there is the official opening and closing prayer which are often taken by Christian and Islamic clerics. Even right inside our state houses not to speak of campuses are chapels and mosques. Every year governments both at the federal and state levels sponsor delegates on holy pilgrimage to Israel and Saudi Arabia. To say the least there is a national mosque and a national ecumenical centre at the Federal Capital City, Abuja. McKinnon (2021) observed that although, the constitution of Nigeria claims that Nigeria is a secular state, yet the same constitution recognises Christianity and Islam. At the individual level, three religions are often practiced simultaneously by most people. Meaning, the Nigerian people have been living with African Traditional Religion, Christianity and Islam. However, the United States Department of State’s survey in (2022) revealed that Christianity and Islam are the most generally practiced faiths in Nigeria. There have been intermarriages of practitioners of the religions. Whereas, some people stay clear of any of the three religions, others practice one or two of the three. Mbaegbu (2024) establishes a fact that “more than seventy percent of Nigerians said they practiced their religion at least several times a week.” Anele and Dibia (2024) observed that in spite of the overbearing influence of religion on Nigeria, one of the major problems Nigeria has had to battle incessantly is religious hypocrisy, bigotry and intolerance. Radicalism and fanaticism coupled with illiteracy and poverty have enhanced the spate of religious clashes we have had recently concluded Olayinka (2023). The issue of Muslim-Muslim ticket was almost turning the country to shreds as some people feel they have been side-lined in the scheme of things. Why all these debates around religion are going on religious leaders and practitioners have continued to use religion to exploit unsuspecting masses. It is however ironic that though many Nigerians have had to part with their hard-earned money while many lost loved ones and properties to corrupt religious leaders Mbaegbu (2024) showed that “Nigerians view religious leaders as more trustworthy, less corrupt than public institutions”

Methodology

Though, Ahmed Yerima has well over twenty published plays which cover various aspects of our lives as a nation, *The Bishop* and *The Angel* are selected for this current study for the purpose of identifying and discussing religious malpractices represented in the plays. The study employs critical textual method to closely scrutinise the selected plays with particular attention to themes and style.

A Synopsis of *The Angel*, *The Twist*, *The Mirror Cracks*, *The Bishop*

The Angel is essentially about Otunba frantically looking for God to help heal his wife, Rachel from a kidney disease. In *The Twist*, Reverend Noah is also seeking for a miracle amnesty for his son who has been condemned to death by hanging. *The Mirror Cracks* presents Ambassador Gabi putting final touches to the burial arrangement of his son Supo who passed on while on a peace keeping mission outside the country. *The Bishop* satirizes both the clergy and the laity as both groups are only using religion to meet their needs.

Major Findings

The study discovers through a critical analysis of the selected texts that among other things that religion is represented as a domain of hypocrisy, classism, immorality, gambling and corruption. It is also discovered that religion serves as a coping strategy for many people who are looking for ways out of the many socio-political and economic challenges of post/neocolonial Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

Religious Hypocrisy as a Theme in Selected Plays of Ahmed Yerima

Yerima does not seem to bother much about violent religious clashes but on the hypocrisy of some religious practitioners who against the tenets of their religions have chosen the path pluralism while others display an open disregard for the African Traditional religion. That is the popular thing among many practitioners of religion in post-independence Nigeria.

Since we have identified religion as a burning issue in postcolonial Nigeria that Yerima gives careful attention to, we also engage this phenomenon to

establish the extent to which Yerima is in tune with postcolonial realities in his works.

It is evident that religion is a major aspect of Nigeria worst affected by corrupt practices. Thus, it is a main thrust of Yerima's post-colonial themes. One of the main issues of the theme of religion as is dramatised by Yerima is the hypocrisy or insincerity of most religious practitioners. According to the examined texts, both Christianity and African Traditional Religion are guilty of practitioners' duality and inconsistency. Majority of religion adherents are only practising it just for them to use it to satisfy their material needs. Most of the characters who profess Christianity in the plays being investigated are also practising secretly tenets of African Indigenous Religion to get their problems solved. They neither believe in 'though he slay me, yet will I trust in him' according to (Job 13:15).

Nor what the Biblical Shadrach, Meshach, and Abednego said to king Nebuchadnezzar in the book of (Daniel 3:17-18) 'If it be so, our God whom we serve is able to deliver us from the burning fiery furnace, and he will deliver us out of thine hand, O king. But if not, be it known unto thee, O king, that we will not serve thy gods, nor worship the golden image which thou hast set up which they quote copiously to preach to others.

Religious Crossing as a Theme in the Selected Plays of Ahmed Yerima

In the same vain, characters who carry chieftaincy titles that are associated with African Traditional Religion go to church so that they will not be labelled pagans. Such characters view Christianity fashionable and more socially acceptable thus cynics like Kaka in *Uncle Venyil* will be going to church in spite of their disbelief in the power of God. Kaka is a good specimen of Nigerians who go to church just to show off their newly acquired dresses and to ensure they are buried by the church at their death. Another wrong selfish reason for rich and well to do people going to church and supporting the church financially is noted in *Otunba*, *Gabi* and *Tundun* in *The Angel* and *The Mirror Cracks* respectively. Their own purpose is to secure a permanent seat in the church both for themselves and their family members.

Religious Immorality As a Theme in the Selected Plays of Ahmed Yerima

Furthermore, morality forms another recurrent theme in the selected Yerima's religious plays. Although morality or what is moral can be relative,

there are basic human ethical standards that all humans are expected to uphold. For instance, incest which is a major ethical concern in the plays being investigated is a taboo to almost all religions in the world. To become guilty of such is considered a grave offence that not only has terrible consequences while the offender is alive, it is believed to have adverse results even in after life. On sighting Chief Gbadegesin's swollen corpse, Baba Ajagbe and Ifagbayi who are steeped in the traditional African ways immediately conclude that he must have committed a grave abomination while alive. In *The Mirror Cracks*, Supo is evil on moral grounds. Also, Bishop Daku, Gabi as well as Tundun, and Kaka in *Uncle Venyil* are all frauds; In *The Wives*, Chief Gbadegesin is a hypocrite. Chief, while alive, held a high office in a traditional secret society yet he professed to be a Christian publicly.

Religious Corruption as a Theme in the Selected Plays of Ahmed Yerima

Internal corruption is another theme that is explored by the religion inclined works of Ahmed Yerima. Much like the economic and political climes, the religious cycles are also bedevilled by mega corrupt practices. For instance, as the plays exposed, a typical Nigerian post-colonial cleric unlike the white missionaries will rather pursue promotion into higher offices and placement into money-spinning assemblies than engaging in evangelism, soul-winning and discipleship. In *The Twist*, Reverend Noah, claims:

'Noah: In my parish, what amazed me was how ... men, deacons, church workers, were willing to give up their souls for positions. [...] Those who had joined the secret cult and lost the elections, came dejected, they came to make confessions of their trials...' 4.

In post/neo-colonial Nigeria, money has become the god for many people. People will even use God to make money rather than use money to serve and worship God. Naira other than the Biblical command of rescuing the sinner from everlasting damnation is now the pursuit of many Christians as well as their leaders.

Classism As a Theme in the Selected Religious Plays of Ahmed Yerima

Aside the lust for money by some religious leaders. The plays also comment on the acts of regard for people's social, economic and political class and gross disregard for Biblical doctrines. For instance, the Bible never states that polygamy is a sin for Christians aside the fact that monogamy is a

requirement for anyone who aspires to be a Bishop or Deacon. The refusal of the church to bury Anthony in *Uncle Venyil* on the ground that he is a polygamist is hypocritical when the same church in *The Mirror Cracks* proceeds to bury Supo who embodies evil. Supo is not only a liar by showing a Christian character before his parents as well as their friends and associates, while he is actually a killer and rapist. The Bishop himself, when he gets to know that Supo committed the sin of fornication with a minor does not stop the burial process because of his hypocritical consideration for the social status of Supo's parents.

Religious Gambling As a Theme in the Selected Plays of Ahmed Yerima

Yerima explores the practice of religious gambling in *Uncle Venyil*. The character, Kaka in *Uncle Venyil* embodies syncretism in religion; she yields to the much forcefully repressed African traditional religious beliefs and rituals as it becomes glaring that Christianity as portrayed in the play cannot deliver her son from imprisonment.

Religious Equality As a Theme in the Selected Plays of Ahmed Yerima

Succinctly, in the plays, Yerima is teaching that all religions are equal. He presents characters who direly need supernatural assistance and are overtly focused on where nothing comes from initially only to be forced eventually to seek help in places they once maligned. It is part of the decolonialism temper of the post-colonial playwrights to seek to place Africa at all levels and fronts on equal pedestal with Euro-American practices. In fact, Yerima gives more honour to African Traditional Religion because almost all his characters in the religion inclined plays got solution they seek in other religions in the African Traditional Religion.

The plays under review have corroborated the fact that part of post/neo-colonial problems that Yerima examined in his plays is religion as it is being practised in the post-independence era. The playwright however submits through his works that no sinner will go unpunished that even the reward for their evil begins while here on earth.

Proverbs, folkloric traditions as well-known religious concepts are deployed by the author to propel his storylines in the plays. The plays under investigation are mono act plays. All equally have main and sub plots which are sustained by single setting each. The classical unity of time is also observed in the plays.

The Angel is set in the living room of Otunba, who is seen praying to “Father” for his wife, Rachel, to be healed from a kidney disease. Reverend Noah is also seeking for a miracle amnesty for his son who has been condemned to death by hanging in *The Twist*. The setting of *The Twist* is the sitting room of Chief Ojuolape who is first presented while making arrangements for a befitting burial for his late son, Dolapo. The beginning scene of the play presents Revd. Noah stepping into Chief Ojuolape’s living room to solicit for mercy for his son who is sentenced to death by hanging for killing Otunba Ojuolape’s son. The plays portray the various reactions of people to death especially the trauma associated with the death of a beloved one. It is only in *The Bishop* that we have initial actions taking place on stage, in the other plays much is reported than acted. Rachel becomes ill because Christopher died two years earlier in *The Angel*. Ambassador Gabi in *The Mirror Cracks* is presented putting final touches to the burial arrangement of his son Supo who passed on while on a peace keeping mission outside the country. Supo’s death is reported by a sixteen years old girl.

Religion As a Coping Strategy in the Selected Plays of Ahmed Yerima

That religion in post/neo-colonial Nigeria is only a means to an end is tragic. It is a coping strategy for many who see religion as an escape route out of existential complexities. *The Angel* portrays Otunba on his knees praying frantically to ‘God’ for his sick wife.

‘Otunba: ‘...Father, do something. Can’t you do something to help her get better? [...] Send something, Send us a miracle, Father, save Rachel ...save my beautiful jewel’4.

Unlike Otunba who staunchly believes in God’s ability to heal his wife, Rachel, in *The Angel*, Kaka, though, keeps praying incessantly for the release of her son, Venyil, from detention does not really believe in miracles or God’s intervention. For the average person in post/neo-colonial Nigeria, religion is the shelter much needed for solace in the face of harsh post-independence realities. Religion is not much about pure worship and love for God but a tool or coping mechanism. In fact, for people like Kaka, the church is a veritable avenue to display their wealth and show off her new dresses. To an extent, the Kaka of the post-independence Nigeria cannot be blamed because the religious houses have failed to practice the doctrines they preached. For example, Kaka’s situation reveals the fact that the

church as instructed by God should be taking care of widows and the less privileged but now are exploiting them. Kaka was angry that the church made her sell her fattest goat to buy a piece of cloth the church should have bought for her. Thus she withdraws her contribution to the church as a way of punishing the church.

'Kaka: ...God! So I have resolved to punish the church for making me sell my fattest goat. I have the money, but I shall pay a naira every Sunday until Venyil is out of prison, and I have a good reason to wear the dress to church to glorify God. But if I should die before Venyil come[s] out, or I finish paying the balance of their money is in the old snuff tin under the bed. I want to go to the gate of heaven singing, not explaining to God how I sold my goat and still kept the money from the church...'4

The study shows that African Traditional Religion is unconsciously represented in biased light. It is presented as an undesirable religion. For instance, Iyagana who is Bishop's paternal aunt hypnotises Bishop with her spiritual powers. In Uncle Venyil too, Venyil, in an attempt to seek revenge crosses into African Traditional religion that is said to animalise him as reported in the following excerpt:

'Kaka: '...at the compound, my son became an animal. With one swift move, like an eagle, he perched on a white cockerel. And in a wild dance, he went to the ancestral shrine, where like a lioness, he bit off the head of the cockerel. He drank the blood, oh God, my son drank the blood of the dying cockerel, still jerking, still twisting. Then wildly he bathed himself, Boyi and the shrines in blood. Boyi started to beat his little drum first in one slow rhythm, you should have seen my son dance. Gradually, he started to spin like one possessed, until he fell, exhausted, [...] my son. He is theirs now. They will initiate him into their cult'4.

Unlike the practice in Nigeria where almost everybody subscribes actively to one religious persuasion or the other, the playwright under review has deliberately used very minimal quantity of characters as a way to show that even with just a few sample of Nigerians dramatic literature can accommodate in a text or stage, much of the common traits of the larger population has been objectively represented. *The Twists* has two characters; Revd. Noah and Otunba Ojuolape. *The Wives* has seven people. *The Mirror Cracks* has eight characters. *Uncle Venyil* has a somewhat large amount of characters. Aside about thirteen visible people, there are the drummers, the dancers and the people under masks. In spite of the fact that the play has

.....

a slightly large amount of characters, the core of the play rotates more about Kaka, her two children: Venyil and Zwan, as well as Boyi the young drummer boy.

Conclusion

Sociologically, almost every level of the society is ably represented in the plays' character construct. While the plays attempt to convey such a message that is common and thus use almost similar methods, a degree of diversity is observed in the settings. Except Uncle Venyil with characters pulled out from the lower wrong of the society. Other plays that depict the theme of post-independence tragedy in religion deployed characters typical of upper-middle social, political and economic class. This gives rise to a claim that Yerima's dramas exhibit clear cut classism that exist in society. His are works that allow all levels of the society sufficient representation. For instance, a play that focuses on issues around the proletariats, characters who are part of the working class are the ones brought to handle it. Matters affecting the upper class are role played by members of the same class. Thus, in his plays, there are diplomats, professors, traditional rulers, herbalists, teachers, dancers, musicians, beggars among others.

The social and economic class of Yerima's characters in religion focused dramas and the observance of classical unity of time in them are the reasons we can give for the lack of much development of the characters aside what is already presented at the initial stages of the plays. Almost all of them are stock characters who have similar titles they carry in real life because of their taste for avarice and materialistic tendencies. They are all or either Bishop, Reverend, Chief, Otunba, and Ambassador among others. These titles are the exclusive preserve of the members of the upper class only. They are class markers.

References

- Adeyemi. L. (2021). Literature and History: Study of Nigerian Indigenous Historical Novels. *Yoruba Study Review*. Vol 1(1) pp.1-12.
- Agboola. M. O. (2020). Religious Dislocation, Socio-economic Dysfunction and the Politics of Terrorism in Ahmed Yerima's Heart of Stone. *International Journal of Integrative Humanism*, 12.1
- Anele, Miracle & Dibia, Peter (2024). Religious Insincerity as a Major Challenge to Nigeria's Infrastructural Development: A Kap Analysis on Imo State

- Residents. *IMSU Journal of Communication Studies*, 8(1) 101-110.
<https://doi.org/10.05281/Zenodo.12693645>.
- Chalise. K.R. (2022). Ranahar: Textuality of History, Culture and Politics. *Journal of Balkumari College*. Vol 10 (1) pp 34-38
- Lawal, Nurudeen (2023). 'I am Trying to Redefine the Playwright: An Interview with Ahmed Yerima'. *Alicante Journal of English Studies*.39, 163-175.
- Mbaegbu, Raphael (2024) Nigerians View Religious Leaders as More Trustworthy Than, Less Corrupt than Public Institutions. *Afro barometer Dispatch No.900 1-22*.
- McKinnon, Andrew (2021) Christians, Muslims and Traditional Worshipers in Nigeria: Estimating the Relative Proportions from Eleven Nationally Representative Social Surveys. *Review of Religious Research*.63(2)303-315.
- Noon. Y. (2021) Jihade Afghan, Historicism, New Historicism and 'Qalla Jangee' a Novel (Post Modern Reading) Makhz 10. 47205/makhz.2021(2-iv)10. Pp129-146.
- Olayinka, Olumuyiwa (2023) Historical Realities and the Post-Colonial Discourse in Selected Ahmed Yerima's Plays. Doctoral Thesis Submitted to the Department of Languages and Literatur, Lead City University, Ibadan.
- Olayinka, Olumuyiwa (2024) Collaboration as a Tool for Nation Building: A Reading of Ahmed Yerima's The Lottery Ticket. *International Journal of Contemporary Research in Humanities*, 2 (1) 23-28.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/Zenodo.14875002>.
- Salman. M.A. (2021) Wordsworth's Lucy Poems as the Reflections of French Revolution: A New Historicist Study. *Journal of Education College, Wasit University*. [10.31185/eduj.vol2.15545.2321](https://doi.org/10.31185/eduj.vol2.15545.2321). Vol 2(45) pp 513-546
- The Holy Bible (2023). King James Version Job 13:15, and Daniel 3:17-18. Ibadan: Beulahland Bible Publishers.
- United States Department of State. (2022) 2022 Report on International Religious Freedom: Nigeria.
- Yerima, Ahmed (1998). *The Bishop and the Soul with Thank You Lord*. Ibadan: Kraft Books Ltd.
- Yerima. Ahmed (2004). *The Angel and Other Plays*. Ibadan: Kraft Books.